

NODES

Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

NODES – Nord OvestDigitale e Sostenibile

Network of Teachers

SPOKE 4 – Digital and Sustainable Mountain

DELIVERABLE DN.N27

Version history

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Creation of a network of teachers on outdoor education and learning.

In 2023, the Groupe de Recherche en Education à l'Environnement et à la Nature de l'Université de la Vallée d'Aoste (GREEN-Univda) initiated a network of educators dedicated to outdoor education and learning in the regions of Piedmont and Valle d'Aosta. To operationalize this new network, GREEN-Univda developed a Sensitive Dance work program. We hypothesized that Sensitive Dance, primarily engaging the kinesthetic channel, can enhance a child's innate connection with Nature. The study compared the effects of Sensitive Dance lessons to physical education classes on children's connectedness to Nature, using psychometric scales to measure this connection. By examining the potential benefits of Sensitive Dance, this research seeks to contribute to understanding and promoting biophilia in children.

A) Connection with Nature and Sensitive Dance

Creation of a network of teachers on outdoor education and learning.

Introduction

In 2023, the Groupe de Recherche en Education à l'Environnement et à la Nature de l'Université de la Vallée d'Aoste (GREEN-Univda) initiated a network of teachers dedicated to biophilic outdoor education and learning in the regions of Piedmont and Aosta Valley. This newly formed network consists of approximately ten female teachers, ranging in age from 30 to 55, who are employed at primary schools in Quart Villair (Aosta Valley) and Ivrea (Piedmont). These teachers possess a blend of humanistic and scientific expertise. To operationalize this new network, GREEN-Univda developed a Sensitive Dance work program. This project aims to identify tools that can enhance biophilia, a human's innate connection with Nature. Sensitive Dance, primarily engaging the kinesthetic channel, is hypothesized to communicate primarily with the corporeal and sensory aspects of practitioners. While less evident, it may also involve emotional aspects and a degree of regression. Additionally, it could engage cognitive aspects related to movement organization, memory of simple sequences, and spatial orientation.

Main Objective

The primary objective of this research is to falsify the hypothesis that Sensitive Dance has no effect on children's biophilia. This hypothesis is based on the personal experiences and testimonies of numerous sensitive dancers, which often align with descriptions provided by those who have experienced deep ecology.

School Selection and Teacher Reference

The project seeks to improve children's connection with Nature through outdoor activities, utilizing Sensitive Dance as preparatory action. Numerous schools in Aosta Valley and Piedmont were approached, resulting in several applications. Schools in Quart Villair (Valle d'Aosta) and Ivrea (Piemonte) were selected based on individual and collective interviews with their teaching staff.

Research Topic Organization

Considering the configuration of the selected schools, the GREEN-Univda developed specific research topics for each comprehensive institute. With the Quart Villair (primary school) comprehensive institute, a basic path of outdoor educational activities was designed. The Comprehensive Institute of Ivrea (primary school) developed an environmental awareness program utilizing Sensitive Dance.

Data Collection Tool Selection

The GREEN Univda selected three psychometric scales: the Connectedness to Nature Scale (CNS; Mayer & Frantz, 2004), the Dispositional Empathy with Nature (DEN; Tam, 2013), and the Children's Affective Attitude toward Nature (CAAN; Cheng & Moore, 2012). These scales measure the degree of individual connection with Nature, empathy towards Nature, and affective attitude towards Nature, respectively.

Meetings

To organize the program of activities, meetings were conducted with the involved groups of teachers, prioritizing in-person meetings but resorting to online meetings when necessary.

Research Program Development

This project focuses on enhancing biophilia, an innate but underdeveloped form of empathy towards Nature. Sensitive Dance is explored as a potential tool to improve biophilia, primarily engaging kinesthetic intelligence and fostering social skills. The research investigates the hypothesis that "Sensitive Dance does not influence connectedness towards Nature". Fifth-grade students are involved in the experimental observations, with the treatment group participating in Sensitive Dance lessons and the control group participating in physical education classes. Both groups completed a test measuring connectedness with Nature before and after the five-week period. The project delves deeper into the concept of biophilia as an asymmetrical form of empathy, examining its development stages and key factors. It also explores effective methods for nurturing biophilia.